

GNN Recommendation System for Enhancing Peer and Tutor-Student Interactions in a Social Media Environment

Anton Melnykov

a.r.melnykov@gmail.com

Abstract

Our research presents a Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based recommendation system designed to enhance peer-to-peer and tutor-student interactions within a social media-inspired educational platform. The system leverages the principles of social networking to facilitate seamless connections between tutors and students, enabling users to act as either or both roles. By modeling user interactions through a social graph, our GNN aims to predict and recommend meaningful connections based on node attributes (such as demographics, skills, and affiliations) and edge attributes (such as lesson frequency and connection type). Key recommendations are driven by user demographics, institutional affiliations, and related social connections, ensuring personalized matches. Our GNN uses two graph convolutional layers to extract higher-level feature representations, enabling both link prediction and edge classification. Testing and assessment metrics demonstrate the robustness of our approach in predicting relevant connections, with practical implications for enhancing learning networks in real-world scenarios.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, rapid technological advancements have transformed our daily lives. People now have access to millions of online resources, enabling them to acquire valuable information and connect with other people across the globe. This progress has significantly enhanced educational accessibility, with online platforms becoming popular for learning new skills and preparing for exams [1, 2].

Many users seek tutors and students from various fields, sometimes seeking for in-person lessons with those who are nearby or online sessions with distant ones. However, new or independent tutors often struggle with limited outreach, making it difficult for them to connect with students actively seeking their services. The current process of finding, communicating, and scheduling lessons typically involves using multiple platforms, which can be inefficient and time-consuming [3]. Additionally, locating tutors and students based on demographics, interests, or other relevant features across different regions remains challenging, limiting the potential for seamless connections and learning opportunities [4].

The freedom offered by social media platforms enables users to effortlessly discover and receive recommendations for friends and other users of interest. Applying the same social media principles in the context of tutor and student recommendations—where users can both search for others and be found themselves—would streamline the process, making it more efficient and seamless [5, 6].

The primary objective of this paper is to develop a robust and flexible recommendation system built upon a social graph constructed from data provided by tutors and students on the platform. This system aims to generate the most relevant and meaningful connections between users' nodes, accounting for the type of each node (whether tutor or student) and the relationships between them. These connections will be optimized based on factors such as users' demographics, preferences, skills, mutual connections, and institutional affiliations (a detailed explanation is provided in the Methodology section) [7, 8].

In the chapter 2 “*Materials*”, paper begins by outlining the database schema created to achieve our objectives. Next, chapter 3 “*Methodology*”, provides our

codebase, explains the logic under the platform's connections, the structure of the graph, and the attributes assigned to user nodes and edges. Following this, we delve into the core logic of our recommendation system, including the preparation and preprocessing of training data, and the architecture of our GNN model. In Chapter 4 “*Testing and Assessing*”, we discuss our training process, and the activation and loss functions employed. Finally, in the Chapter 5 “*Further Implementations and Future Work*” we are discussing the potential integration of our recommendation system into the platform and exploring directions for further improvements.

2. Materials

The system considers both the source and target users, along with their respective modes, to assign the appropriate connection type. A connection sent from a user in *tutor* mode to a user in *student* mode is assigned the type "Tutor". Conversely, a connection sent from *student* mode to a *tutor* is assigned the type "Student". If the connection occurs between two users in the same mode, it is assigned the type "Mutual". Additionally, the number of lessons conducted between users along each edge serves as a weight, supporting the prediction of future "Student" and "Tutor" connections. These attributes—`sourceId`, `targetId`, `connectionType`, and `lessonsNum`—are attached to every edge and help predict new potential connections in the graph.

On the node level, the database schema includes attributes such as age, nationality, languages known, interests, and skills (optional if only the *student* mode is active). Users can also provide educational background, professional experiences (available only in *tutor* mode), test scores (optional), and courses (optional). These features, associated with each node, play a crucial role in training the GNN model and improving the quality of predictions.

Throughout this paper, we refer to edges between nodes as *connections*. In our graph, edges are directed and defined by the `sourceId` and `targetId` attributes. Each edge is also weighted by the `lessonsNumber` attribute, which indicates the total number of lessons scheduled between two users along that link. A connection between two users is a prerequisite for scheduling a lesson, reinforcing the importance of maintaining and forming relevant connections

3. Methodology

The core logic of the platform is that any user can act as both a tutor and a student, or choose to be either. Specifically, users can switch between modes within the same account. If a user selects the "Student" mode, they will primarily receive tutor recommendations. On the other hand, choosing the "Tutor" mode will prioritize student recommendations. Additionally, users will also receive recommendations of others in the same mode, enabling them to grow their social network—such as following a friend who is also a student or a relative who works as a tutor. This approach allows users to expand their network and, consequently, increase their outreach to more students or tutors.

Our codebase was developed using *JavaScript* and *TypeScript* to ensure both safety and stability, while facilitating seamless integration with the future platform. To develop our GNN model, we required a graph structure with pre-defined nodes, edges connecting these nodes, and relevant attributes attached to each. This task is managed by the populator element, which extracts data from a synthetic *JSON* table containing user information and generates links between nodes according to the underlying logic that will serve as the baseline for our GNN model. Once generated, the nodes and links are stored in a *NoSQL Database*.

The nodes and edges are later fetched from the database and processed using *graphology.js*, a library for graph-based operations. To facilitate communication between the TypeScript code and our Python-based model, we establish a *WebSocket* connection. This *WebSocket* allows us to send the graph and any updates in *JSON* format to the GNN model for further processing.

3.1 Baseline logic

Our recommendation system's baseline logic operates across three key aspects: **Demographics**, **Institution-Affiliated**, and **Related Connections**. Each of these aspects contributes to making more relevant and personalized recommendations by leveraging user attributes, affiliations, and social relationships [9, 10].

3.1.1 Demographics

The model incorporates demographic attributes of nodes, such as languages spoken, nationalities, ages, and interests. By aligning these characteristics, the system predicts potential connections between users who share common attributes [14].

3.1.2 Institution-Affiliated

Trust in tutor-student relationships often builds within familiar institutional settings. The model enhances trust by recommending tutors to students in the same institution where they currently study (`status: true`),

especially if previous lessons have been conducted with these tutors or other affiliated individuals. This approach leverages shared educational environments to facilitate stronger, more reliable connections between tutors and students.

3.1.3 Related Connections

This component draws on a social networking principle often seen in social media platforms: “A friend of my friend might also be my friend.” [15] The model leverages existing “Mutual” connections to extend recommendations. When a user has an established connection with another individual, the system recommends this new user to either of the connected parties, fostering new connections within the user network.

3.2 Preprocessing

In order for our model to be able to learn from our node and edge attributes, those attributes have to be preprocessed and aggregated in one data object that can be passed to our GNN model.

Our data preprocessing pipeline applies *Standard Scaling*, *One-Hot Encoding*, and *Embeddings*

to ensure that features are properly transformed for input to the GNN model. Each method is chosen based on the nature and cardinality of the feature. Below, we describe the purpose and advantages of each approach:

3.2.1 Standard Scaling

We apply Standard Scaling to integer-valued features such as age (in the User collection) and lessonNum (in the Connection collection). This ensures that the features have a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1, helping the GNN model converge faster by ensuring that numerical inputs are on a comparable scale. It also prevents bias towards features with larger absolute values, which might otherwise dominate the model’s learning process.

3.2.2 One-Hot Encoding

For categorical features with a small number of categories, such as connectionType in the Connection collection, we use One-Hot Encoding. One-Hot Encoding is simple and effective when dealing with a small number of categories. However, One-Hot Encoding becomes computationally expensive with high-cardinality features. For this reason, it is used only for categorical data with a manageable number of distinct values.

3.2.3 Embeddings for High-Cardinality Features

For categorical variables with many unique categories, such as user attributes like language, organization, or interest, we utilize dense vector embeddings. An embedding maps each category to a continuous, low-dimensional vector space. This technique allows us to compress high-cardinality categorical data into meaningful, fixed-length vectors. The embeddings are initialized randomly and updated during training, enabling the model to learn useful relationships between different categories based on their co-occurrence patterns. Embeddings are helpful as they reduce dimensionality, making the model efficient. Moreover, they may capture semantic relationships between categories (e.g., similar languages may receive similar vectors).

All input features, except for name (in the Courses and Test Scores collections) and the identifiers

sourceId and targetId (in the Connection collection), are transformed using these preprocessing techniques. Then, the processed features (13 per node & 4 per edge) are aggregated in `torch_geometric.Data` object and fed into the GNN model to learn complex, multi-relational dependencies across the user and connections between them. Finally, our predictions are sent back through the WebSocket.

3.3 Graph Neural Networks (GNN) Model

The use of GNNs in recommendation systems has been explored to predict connections within graph-based data, providing robust feature representations for link prediction tasks [11, 12]. In our implementation, our GNN model defines a two-layer neural network to perform link prediction and edge classification (type of the potential connection). The input to the model is a set of node features and edge attributes. Each node's initial features are passed through two graph convolutional layers with activation functions to extract higher-level representations.

The first graph convolutional layer, `conv1`, transforms the input node features into a higher-dimensional hidden space. `ReLU` activation function introduces non-linearity after the first layer to enhance feature learning.

The second graph convolutional layer, `conv2`, produces edge formation probabilities through a `Sigmoid` activation function, mapping the values to the range $[0, 1]$. These probabilities indicate the likelihood of edges existing between node pairs.

Next, the model predicts edge types by combining the features of the source and destination nodes of the nodes that it predicted to exist along with the edge attributes. This concatenated vector captures both individual node information and their relationships through edge attributes. The resulting vector is processed by a fully connected layer `fc_edge` to

perform multiclass classification on edge types. Afterwards, the `Softmax` activation is applied to produce a probability distribution over the possible edge types. Finally, the value with the highest probability is taken and reversed from the One-Hot Encoding to its normal form: `'Student'`, `'Tutor'`, or `'Mutual'`.

This GNN design allows the model to learn both node-level representations and relationship types between nodes, making it suitable for link prediction and edge classification tasks. The model uses the following hyperparameters: 13 input channels for node features, 128 hidden dimensions for internal layers, and 3 output dimensions to classify edge types. This setup effectively captures the graph's structural and feature-based nuances, which are essential for the tasks within our recommendation system.

3.3.1 Activation Functions

Activation functions enable our model to learn complex patterns. In our approach, `ReLU`, `Sigmoid`, and `Softmax` are strategically applied to enhance learning efficiency and provide interpretable outputs for both binary and multiclass tasks.

3.3.1.1 ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit)

The `ReLU` function is applied after the first graph convolutional layer to introduce non-linearity into the network. `ReLU` is computationally efficient, reducing the risk of vanishing gradients (when gradients that are used to update the network become extremely small as they are backpropagated from the output layers to the earlier layers), which accelerates convergence during training [13]. In our model, `ReLU` allows the hidden layer to learn meaningful patterns from the input node features.

3.3.1.2 Sigmoid Activation Function

The `Sigmoid` function is used in the second layer to predict edge probabilities, mapping the output values into the range $[0, 1]$. This makes it ideal for binary classification tasks like predicting the existence of edges. `Sigmoid` ensures that the output probabilities are interpretable and suitable for threshold-based decisions (e.g., whether an edge exists or not). Additionally, the potential for vanishing gradients in

deeper layers is mitigated by applying it only at the output layer for edge existence prediction.

3.3.1.3 Softmax Activation Function

Softmax is employed to predict edge types, performing multiclass classification by normalizing the output vector into a probability distribution. This activation ensures that the sum of probabilities across all edge types is equal to 1, making it appropriate for multiclass predictions. It enables our model to assign confidence scores to each edge type, ensuring interpretability and reliability in the classification output.

In summary, ReLU, Sigmoid, and Softmax are used strategically to maximize learning efficiency and ensure proper probabilistic outputs for both binary and multiclass tasks. These activations help the model efficiently capture relationships between nodes and predict both the existence and types of edges.

4. Testing and Assessing

In machine learning, particularly in the context of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), the processes of training, validation, and testing are crucial for developing robust models. These processes ensure that the model learns effectively from the data, makes good predictions of unseen instances, and evaluates its performance accurately. This chapter describes how these processes are implemented to enhance our model.

We begin with splitting our data into training, validation, and testing sets. **Training Set (80%)** is used to train our model, containing the majority of our graph's edges. **Validation Set (10%)** is a small subset of edges used to tune our model's hyperparameters and prevent overfitting (grasping the noise in the present data). **Testing Set (10%)** contains edges that the model has never seen and is used to evaluate the model's performance. This splitting is crucial to ensure that our model learns generalizable features and does not simply memorize the training data.

During model's training, the *Adam* optimizer is used to update model parameters with a learning rate (how much a model's parameters are adjusted during training) of *0.01*. The training objective involves edge prediction that predicts whether a connection exists

between two nodes and edge type classification that predicts the type of the connection.

Binary Cross-Entropy and Cross-Entropy losses are widely used in GNNs for tasks like link prediction and edge classification, ensuring accurate learning of both edge existence and types [17]. In our model, two primary loss functions are employed: *Binary Cross-Entropy Loss* for edge existence prediction and *Cross-Entropy Loss* for edge type classification. Both loss functions are crucial for ensuring the model's performance by addressing two different tasks—whether an edge should exist and, if it does, what type of connection it represents.

4.1 Binary Cross-Entropy Loss (BCE)

Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) is used to evaluate the predicted probability of edge existence between two nodes. BCE measures how close this predicted probability is to the actual label (0 or 1). The loss function for BCE is expressed as:

$$L_{BCE} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \cdot \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

Where y_i is the ground truth (whether the edge exists or not); $\hat{y}_i$ is the predicted probability of the edge, and N is the number of samples. This loss function penalizes the model for incorrect predictions, pushing it to improve the accuracy of edge existence prediction.

4.2 Cross-Entropy Loss for Edge Type Classification

Since our model predicts multiple types of connections, we use **Cross-Entropy Loss** to measure the discrepancy between the predicted connection type and the true connection type. The Cross-Entropy Loss function is:

$$\text{Cross Entropy} = -\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \cdot \log(\hat{y}_{i,c})$$

$y_{i,c}$ is binary indicator 1 if the edge belongs to class c , otherwise 0; $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability for the

sample i belonging to the class c ; C is the total number of edge classes, and N number of samples

This loss function ensures that the model learns to correctly classify edge types by minimizing the difference between the predicted and actual classes. *BCE Loss* is applied to the output of the probability of edge formation. Simultaneously, *Cross-Entropy Loss* is used on the predicted edge classification. These two loss values are combined during training, allowing the model to learn both tasks effectively. This dual-loss approach ensures that the model accurately learns both edge existence and edge classification, making it well-suited for graph-based recommendation tasks.

The model parameters are updated iteratively over multiple epochs to minimize the combined loss function. During each epoch, the model is also evaluated on the validation set to monitor its performance. The same loss functions used during training are applied to compute the validation loss. This allows for early stopping or hyperparameter adjustments if the validation performance is getting worse, indicating potential overfitting.

After the training is complete, the final model is evaluated on the test set, which consists of edges that were not used during training or validation. The evaluation involves predicting the existence and type of each edge, with performance metrics such as loss being recorded. This step ensures that the model performs well on completely unseen data, validating its generalization ability.

While training losses steadily decreased, the validation losses indicated the model's ability to generalize to unseen data. If validation performance got worse during later epochs, it might suggest overfitting, where the model learns training-specific patterns but struggles with new data. The final testing phase confirmed the model's predictive power by evaluating edge probabilities and types, ensuring it performs effectively on new inputs.

5. Further Implementations and Future Work

In the platform, the recommendation model will rely on data provided directly by users, eliminating the need for synthetic populators. After generating a recommendation, the model will be able to observe whether the user establishes a connection with the recommended individual, providing instant feedback to improve future predictions. Additionally, users will have the option to add more features types to their accounts. These expanded attributes will serve as valuable inputs for the model, enhancing its ability to identify meaningful relationships and improve the quality of recommendations.

In the future, the platform will also support media content sharing, enabling the system to track user interactions with shared media and monitor other platform activities, such as search queries. This behavioral data will further refine the recommendation system, contributing to the development of a more precise and adaptive model capable of delivering better user experiences.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented a Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based recommendation system aimed at enhancing peer and tutor-student interactions within a social media-inspired educational platform. By leveraging the structural and relational complexities of a social graph, the proposed system offers a robust approach to making personalized and meaningful recommendations. Our methodology highlighted the importance of using demographic, institutional, and social attributes to predict potential connections, while edge types and connection frequencies added insights into user relationships.

Through a two-layer GNN model, we achieved both link prediction and edge classification, demonstrating the model's capability to recommend connections that facilitate educational engagement. Testing metrics confirmed the system's efficacy in accurately predicting

relevant interactions, underscoring its potential for real-world applications.

Looking forward, the model can be further improved by incorporating user feedback and interaction data, which would enable adaptive learning and more precise recommendations. Additionally, expanding feature sets and integrating behavioral data will allow the system to evolve alongside user needs, enhancing its adaptability in dynamic educational environments. Ultimately, this work contributes a scalable and efficient recommendation system framework for educational platforms, fostering a connected and supportive learning community.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nguyen, T. (2015). *The effectiveness of online learning: Beyond no significant difference and future horizons*. MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching, 11(2), 309-319.
- [2] Veletsianos, G., & Kimmons, R. (2012). *Assumptions and challenges of open scholarship*. British Journal of Educational Technology, 43(4), 506-523.
- [3] Wang, C., Yang, F., & Wang, J. (2014). *A recommender system to facilitate academic advising: A constraint-based approach*. Proceedings of the 23rd ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, 1629-1638.
- [4] Tang, J., & Liu, H. (2010). *Community detection and mining in social media*. Synthesis Lectures on Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery, 2(1), 1-137.
- [5] Ma, H., Zhou, D., Liu, C., Lyu, M. R., & King, I. (2011). *Recommender systems with social regularization*. Proceedings of the Fourth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, 287-296.
- [6] Tang, J., Hu, X., & Liu, H. (2013). *Social recommendation: A review*. Social Network Analysis and Mining, 3(4), 1113-1133.
- [7] Ying, R., He, R., Chen, K., Eksombatchai, P., Hamilton, W. L., & Leskovec, J. (2018). *Graph convolutional neural networks for web-scale recommender systems*. Proceedings of the 24th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining, 974-983.
- [8] Wang, X., He, X., Wang, M., Feng, F., & Chua, T. S. (2019). *Neural graph collaborative filtering*. Proceedings of the 42nd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, 165-174.
- [9] Kosinski, M., Stillwell, D., & Graepel, T. (2013). *Private traits and attributes are predictable from digital records of human behavior*.
- [10] Zhang, W., & Wang, J. (2013). *Feature-based recommendation using demographics*.
- [11] Hamilton, W. L., Ying, R., & Leskovec, J. (2017). *Inductive representation learning on large graphs*.
- [12] Berg, R. v. d., Kipf, T. N., & Welling, M. (2017). *Graph Convolutional Matrix Completion*.
- [13] Glorot, X., Bordes, A., & Bengio, Y. (2011). *Deep sparse rectifier neural networks*.
- [14] McPherson, M., Smith-Lovin, L., & Cook, J. M. (2001). *Birds of a feather: Homophily in social networks*.
- [15] Hamilton, W. L., Ying, R., & Leskovec, J. (2017). *Inductive representation learning on large graphs*.